

Multi-component one-pot synthesis of novel coumarinyldihydropyridines under solvent free conditions[†]

Kapil Bohra^a, Deepti Sharma^a, Banty Kumar^a, Carl E. Olsen^b, Virinder S. Parmar^a and Ashok K. Prasad^{a*}

^aBioorganic Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007, India

E-mail : ashokenzyme@yahoo.com

^bUniversity of Copenhagen, Faculty of Life Sciences, Department of Natural Sciences, DK-1871 Frederiksberg C, Denmark

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Abstract : A library of fourteen 4-coumarinyl-1,4-dihydropyridines (coumarinyl-1,4-DHP) has been synthesized under modified Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridine synthesis condition by the condensation of 4-formylcoumarin, alkyl acetoacetate and ammonium acetate in the presence of Ba(NO₃)₂ as a catalyst in 58 to 82% yields. Standardization of reaction conditions revealed that 10 mol% of Ba(NO₃)₂ is enough for optimum yields. The developed methodology does not require the use of organic solvents and hence makes the process eco-friendly. The structure of all the coumarinyl-1,4-DHPs were unambiguously established on the basis of IR, ¹H, ¹³C NMR spectroscopy and HRMS data analysis.

Keywords : Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridines, 4-formylcoumarins, barium nitrate, β-ketoesters, ammonium acetate, solvent-free conditions.

Introduction

In 1881 Hantzsch introduced a process for the synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridines (1,4-DHP), which were readily oxidized to pyridines and hence it was accepted as a convenient process for preparation of a variety of substituted pyridines¹⁻⁵. In the biological system, 1,4-DHPs are oxidized to corresponding pyridine derivatives by cytochrome P-450 present in the liver^{6,7}. 1,4-DHPs act as nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) mimics and serves as an antio-redox systems for unsaturated conjugated system as well as carbonyl groups present in living organisms⁸. Furthermore, substituted 1,4-DHPs exhibit a variety of biological activities such as cardiovascular protector, vasodilator, branchodilator, antiatherosclerotic, antitumour, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, geroprotective, antitubercular, calcium channel blocker, nitric oxide (NO) releasing agent and neuroprotective agents⁹⁻¹⁶. Dihydropyridine-based drugs such as nifedipine, amlodipine, nimodipine and many others are used in the treatment of hypertension (Fig. 1).

The synthesis of coumarins and their derivatives has engrossed substantial attention from organic and medicinal chemists for many years as they belong to a class of compounds with proven utility in medicinal chemistry. Coumarin is an important scaffold since several coumarin derivatives are known to be associated with multiple biological activities, especially anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities¹⁷⁻²².

Valenti *et al.*²³ have reported coumarin-DHP conjugates linked through C-8 position of coumarin and C-4 position of 1,4-DHP which showed selective inhibitory effect on cardiac contractility and frequency. Herein, we report the synthesis of a series of fourteen novel coumarinyl-dihydropyridines which have hybrid scaffold comprising coumarin and dihydropyridine moieties having linkage between C-4 position of coumarin to C-4 position of dihydropyridine.

Results and discussion

Multicomponent one-pot synthesis of coumarin-1,4-

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Fig. 1. Representative 4-aryl-1,4-dihydropyridine drugs.

dihydropyridines **13-26** has been carried out by the condensation of 4-formylcoumarin, β -ketoester and ammonium acetate in the presence of catalytic amount of barium nitrate as a heterogeneous catalyst (Scheme 1)^{24,25}. 4-Formylcoumarins **10-12** were synthesized by the reaction of ethyl acetoacetate with resorcinol (**1**), pyrogallol (**2**) and phloroglucinol (**3**) in acidic condition to afford 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (**4**), 7,8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (**5**) and 5,7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (**6**) in 58 to 70% yields (Scheme 1). The hydroxycoumarins **4-6** were methylated with dimethylsulphate in acetone- K_2CO_3 to afford their methoxy derivatives **7-9** in 85 to 90% yields, which on allylic oxidation with selenium dioxide in dioxane afforded 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (**10**), 7,8-dimethoxy-4-formylcoumarin (**11**) and 5,7-dimethoxy-4-formylcoumarin (**12**) in 70 to 80% yields (Scheme 1). Condensation of 4-formylcoumarins **10-12** with β -ketoesters (ethyl, methyl, allyl, *iso*-propyl and *tert*-

butyl acetoacetate) and ammonium acetate in the presence of barium nitrate (10 mol%) afforded dialkyl 4-(methoxycoumarin-4-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-pyridine-3,5-dicarboxylates **13-26** in 58–82% (Scheme 1).

We optimized the catalyst quantity as 10 mol% by varying the quantity of catalyst from 5 to 20 mol%. The results revealed that 10 mol% of $Ba(NO_3)_2$ is the optimum catalyst loading, as the use of less amount of catalyst resulted in the reduction of product yield, while increase in the amount of catalyst did not show any significant effect on the reaction rates as well as yields.

We did not get the desired product **27**, when 5,7-dimethoxy-4-formylcoumarin (**12**) was made to react with *tert*-butyl acetoacetate (Table 1, entry 15). The reason for this might be the steric hindrance between the C-5 position of **12** and the bulky *tert*-butyl group of the *tert*-butyl acetoacetate during the cyclization.

Reagents and conditions : (i) H_2SO_4 , ethyl acetoacetate, 6 h; (ii) Me_2SO_4 , acetone, K_2CO_3 , reflux, 5 h; (iii) SeO_2 , dioxane, reflux, 24 h; (iv) NH_4OAc , $Ba(NO_3)_2$, $CH_3COCH_2COOR_3$ ($R_3 = Et, Me, allyl, i$ -propyl, *t*-butyl), 60 °C, 4–6 h.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 4-coumarinyl-1,4-dihydropyridines.

Table 1. Reaction time and yield of the title compounds

Entries	4-Formyl-coumarin	β -Ketoester	Product	Reaction time (h)	Yield (%)
1.			13	4.0	78
2.			14	4.2	82
3.			15	4.0	80
4.			16	4.0	70
5.			17	5.8	65
6.			18	4.3	75
7.			19	4.5	79
8.			20	4.0	82
9.			21	4.2	69
10.			22	6.0	60
11.			23	5.0	65
12.			24	5.5	68
13.			25	5.6	65
14.			26	6.0	58
15.			27	6.0	<5
					Not isolated

The structures of all the compounds, viz. **4-26** synthesized herein were unambiguously established on the basis of their spectral (IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and HRMS) data analysis. The structures of the known compounds **4-9**²⁶, **10**²⁷, **11**²⁸ and **12**^{29,30} were further confirmed by the comparison of their physical and spectral data with those reported in the literature.

Conclusions

A new series of fourteen coumarinyl-1,4-dihydropyridines have been synthesized in moderate to good yield using $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ as catalyst under solvent-free condition. Optimization of the reaction revealed that 10 mol% of

$\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ is enough for optimum yield of the 4-coumarinyl-1,4-dihydropyridines.

Experimental

Melting points (m.p.) were determined on Büchi M-560 instrument and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 2000 FTIR spectrometer by making KBr discs for all samples. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Jeol alpha-400 spectrometer at 400 MHz and 100.6 MHz or on a Bruker Avance spectrometer at 300 MHz and 75.5 MHz, using TMS as internal standard. HR-ESI-TOF-MS analyses were carried out on a microTOF-Q instrument from Bruker Daltonics, Bremen. Analytical TLCs were performed on pre-coated Merck silica-gel 60F₂₅₄ plates; the spots were detected under UV light. Silica gel (100–200 mesh) was used for column chromatography.

General procedure for the synthesis of 4-formyl-coumarins (**10-12**) :

Hydroxycoumarins **4-6** were synthesized starting from resorcinol (**1**), pyrogallol (**2**) and phloroglucinol (**3**) following the standard literature procedure using ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of H_2SO_4 as catalyst. The hydroxycoumarin **4-6** so obtained was crystallised from ethanol and methylation of free hydroxyls group(s) was carried out with dimethylsulphate in acetone- K_2CO_3 ²⁶ to furnish methylated coumarins **7-9** by crystallisation. Mixture of methylated coumarin **7**, **8** or **9** and selenium dioxide (1.2 equivalent) was refluxed at 102 °C in dioxane for 24 h²⁷⁻³⁰. The reaction mixture was then dissolved in CHCl_3 and filtered to remove selenium dioxide. The residue was then concentrated under vacuum and purified by column chromatography eluting with 60–70% petroleum ether-chloroform mixture.

4-Formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (**10**)²⁷ :

It was obtained as yellow coloured solid in 80% yield. R_f 0.5 (chloroform), m.p. 193–195 °C; IR (cm^{-1} , KBr) : 1720, 1714, 1600, 1590, 1288, 1054 and 847; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 3.90 (3H, s), 6.72 (1H, s), 6.87 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz), 6.92 (1H, dd, J 8.4, 2.8 Hz), 8.50 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 10.07 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 55.8, 101.1, 108.1, 113.2, 122.1, 127.3, 143.7, 156.5, 160.7, 163.3 and 191.7; MS (ESI positive mode) : m/z 204 $[\text{M}]^+$, calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$: 204.

Formyl-7,8-dimethoxycoumarin (11)²⁸ :

It was obtained as yellow coloured solid in 75% yield. R_f 0.4 (chloroform), m.p. 174–177 °C; IR (cm⁻¹, KBr) : 1727, 1704, 1614, 1596, 1289, 1054 and 849; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.96 (6H, s), 6.71 (1H, s), 6.92 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 8.27 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 10.05 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 56.3, 61.5, 109.0, 109.2, 121.6, 122.5, 136.2, 143.7, 148.6, 156.2, 160.1 and 191.6; MS (ESI positive mode) : *m/z* 234 [M]⁺, calcd. for C₁₂H₁₀O₅ : 234.

Formyl-5,7-dimethoxycoumarin (12)^{29,30} :

It was obtained as yellow coloured solid in 70% yield. R_f 0.5 (chloroform), m.p. 199–200 °C; IR (cm⁻¹, KBr) : 1719, 1621, 1337, 1159, 1119 and 843; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.89 (3H, s), 3.93 (3H, s), 6.30 (1H, s), 6.36 (1H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz), 6.50 (1H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz), 10.49 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 55.9, 56.2, 93.8, 95.6, 101.1, 110.5, 148.8, 157.1, 157.4, 160.5, 164.1 and 191.3; HR-ESI-TOF-MS *m/z* 235.0614 ([M+H]⁺), calcd. for [C₁₂H₁₀NO₅+H]⁺ : 235.0601.

General procedure for the synthesis of 4-coumarinyl-1,4-dihydropyridines 13-26 :

To a mixture of 4-formylcoumarin **10-12**, NH₄OAc (1.2 equivalent) and β-keto ester (3.0 equivalent), Ba(NO₃)₂ (10 mol %) was added as catalyst. The reaction mixture was stirred under solvent-free conditions at 60 °C for 4–6 h. On completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice and then extracted with chloroform. The organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under vacuum. Column chromatography of the crude product was done using methanol in chloroform as gradient solvent system to obtain pure compounds **13-26** in 58–82% yield (Table 1).

Diethyl 4-(7'-methoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (13) :

It was obtained as light yellow coloured solid in 78% yield. R_f 0.5 (2% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 219–221 °C; IR (cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3321, 3091, 2981, 1703, 1613, 1277, 1208, 1149, 1048, 837 and 754; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.06 (6H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 2.35 (6H, s), 3.88 (3H, s), 3.95–4.04 (4H, m), 5.37 (1H, s), 6.26 (1H, s), 6.51 (1H, br s), 6.79 (1H, d, *J* 2.8 Hz), 6.91 (1H, dd, *J* 9.6, 2.8 Hz), 8.17 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 14.1, 19.4, 34.6, 55.6, 60.0, 100.1,

103.0, 112.0, 112.1, 112.3, 127.9, 145.4, 155.0, 162.4, 163.5, 165.8 and 166.9; HR-ESI-TOF-MS *m/z* 428.1702 [M+H]⁺, calcd. for [C₂₃H₂₅NO₇+H]⁺ : 428.1704.

Dimethyl 4-(7'-methoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (14) :

It was obtained as yellow coloured solid in 82% yield. R_f 0.4 (2% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 212–215 °C; IR (cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3320, 2950, 1690, 1609, 1215 and 1117; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.13 (3H, s), 2.43 (3H, s), 3.66 (3H, s), 3.72 (3H, s), 3.88 (3H, s), 5.17 (1H, s), 6.01 (1H, s), 6.23 (1H, s), 6.85 (1H, s), 6.90 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.64 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 19.3, 20.9, 50.1, 50.9, 51.4, 55.8, 101.6, 104.5, 106.4, 110.6, 111.8, 112.8, 124.1, 151.2, 153.4, 156.3, 161.6, 162.6 and 167.7; MS (ESI positive mode) : *m/z* 399 [M]⁺, calcd. for C₂₁H₂₁NO₇ : 399.

Diallyl 4-(7'-methoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (15) :

It was obtained as yellow coloured solid in 80% yield. R_f 0.5 (4% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 141–143 °C; IR (cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3412, 3315, 3084, 2957, 1718, 1698, 1647, 1618, 1387, 1375, 1268, 1250, 1219, 1154, 1114 and 1038; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.15 (3H, s), 2.47 (3H, s), 3.86 (3H, s), 4.56–4.69 (4H, m), 5.13–5.36 (4H, m), 5.48 (1H, d, *J* 4.4 Hz), 5.78–5.88 (1H, m), 5.92–6.02 (1H, m), 6.05 (1H, d, *J* 4.4 Hz), 6.24 (1H, s), 6.82 (1H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz), 6.88 (1H, dd, *J* 8.8, 3.2 Hz), 7.68 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 19.3, 19.5, 50.1, 55.6, 64.8, 64.9, 101.2, 102.6, 103.8, 110.6, 111.4, 112.6, 117.7, 118.2, 124.6, 132.1, 132.2, 145.9, 151.8, 156.0, 161.9, 162.4, 165.6, 166.5 and 166.9; HR-ESI-TOF-MS *m/z* 452.1697 ([M+H]⁺), calcd. for [C₂₅H₂₅NO₇+H]⁺ : 452.1704.

Di-iso-propyl 4-(7'-methoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (16) :

It was obtained as light yellow coloured solid in 70% yield. R_f 0.5 (2% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 190–192 °C; IR (cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3277, 3222, 3089, 2980, 1718, 1701, 1689, 1610, 1389, 1272, 1258, 1145, 1088, 1036 and 763; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 0.89 (6H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz), 1.16 (6H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz), 2.33 (6H, s), 3.88 (3H, s), 4.93–4.97 (2H, m), 5.33 (1H, s), 6.26 (1H, s), 6.64

(1H, s), 6.79 (1H, d, *J* 2.4 Hz), 6.92 (1H, dd, *J* 9.2, 2.8 Hz), 8.19 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 19.3, 21.6, 21.9, 34.6, 55.6, 67.2, 100.0, 103.1, 111.9, 112.0, 112.4, 128.5, 145.3, 154.9, 162.4, 163.6, 166.1 and 166.5; HR-ESI-TOF-MS *m/z* 456.2011 ([M+H]⁺), calcd. for [C₂₅H₂₉NO₇+H]⁺ : 456.2017.

Di-tert-butyl 4-(7'-methoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (17) :

It was obtained as light yellow coloured solid in 65% yield. *R_f* 0.4 (2% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 169–172 °C; IR (cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3293, 3235, 3104, 2979, 1701, 1689, 1610, 1498, 1277, 1161, 1148 and 853; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.30 (18H, s), 2.26 (6H, s), 3.84 (3H, s), 5.32 (1H, s), 6.14 (1H, s), 6.48 (1H, s), 6.76 (1H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz), 6.85 (1H, dd, *J* 8.8, 2.0 Hz), 8.17 (1H, d, *J* 9.2 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 19.4, 28.2, 35.3, 55.6, 80.5, 100.2, 103.4, 111.2, 111.8, 111.9, 128.2, 143.8, 155.3, 162.4, 163.45, 163.49 and 166.4; HR-ESI-TOF-MS *m/z* 484.2313 ([M+H]⁺), calcd. for [C₂₇H₃₃NO₇+H]⁺ : 484.2330.

Diethyl 4-(7',8'-dimethoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (18) :

It was obtained as yellow coloured solid in 75% yield. *R_f* 0.4 (2% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 190–192 °C; IR (cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3310, 2982, 1700, 1605, 1291 and 1094; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO) : δ 0.97 (6H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 2.29 (6H, s), 3.78 (3H, s), 3.87–3.92 (7H, m), 5.24 (1H, s), 6.02 (1H, s), 7.16 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 7.91 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 9.06 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, DMSO) : δ 13.9, 18.2, 34.7, 56.2, 59.2, 60.6, 101.0, 108.2, 111.3, 112.5, 122.0, 134.8, 143.7, 146.4, 146.9, 154.8, 160.7, 165.0 and 166.3; HR-ESI-TOF-MS *m/z* 458.1808 [M+H]⁺, calcd. for [C₂₄H₂₇NO₈+H] : 458.1809.

Dimethyl 4-(7',8'-dimethoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (19) :

It was obtained as light yellow coloured solid in 79% yield. *R_f* 0.6 (2% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 170–172 °C; IR (cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3427, 3310, 1705, 1606, 1296, 1215 and 1115; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.08 (3H, s), 2.42 (3H, s), 3.66 (3H, s), 3.72 (3H, s), 3.93 (3H, s), 3.95 (3H, s), 5.23 (1H, s), 5.98 (1H, s), 6.23 (1H, s), 6.92 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 7.46 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 19.3, 20.8, 50.2, 50.9, 51.4, 56.4, 61.4, 104.4, 106.3, 108.5, 111.9, 118.2,

137.0, 148.6, 151.3, 153.5, 155.3, 161.0, 166.4 and 167.7; MS (ESI positive mode): *m/z* 429 [M]⁺, calcd. for C₂₂H₂₃NO₈ : 429.

Diallyl 4-(7',8'-dimethoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (20) :

It was obtained as light yellow coloured solid in 82% yield. *R_f* 0.4 (2% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 188–189 °C; IR (cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3306, 3084, 2940, 1702, 1670, 1648, 1366, 1313, 1296, 1210, 1115 and 1010; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.15 (3H, s), 2.46 (3H, s), 3.961 (3H, s), 3.967 (3H, s), 4.58–4.67 (4H, m), 5.14–5.37 (5H, m), 5.81–6.03 (3H, m), 6.25 (1H, s), 6.91 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz), 7.46 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 17.2, 23.0, 56.3, 61.4, 66.5, 66.6, 108.2, 112.7, 113.1, 120.4, 121.9, 127.4, 130.0, 130.3, 130.8, 136.2, 144.4, 148.1, 151.9, 152.8, 155.6, 156.2, 159.9, 165.8 and 167.3; HR-ESI-TOF-MS *m/z* 504.1615 ([M+Na]⁺), calcd. for [C₂₆H₂₇NO₈+Na]⁺ : 504.1629.

Di-iso-propyl 4-(7',8'-dimethoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (21) :

It was obtained as light yellow coloured solid in 69% yield. *R_f* 0.5 (2% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 198–199 °C; IR (cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3312, 3247, 3104, 2979, 2937, 1702, 1676, 1603, 1492, 1378, 1295, 1211, 1094, 1012 and 759; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 0.94 (6H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz), 1.16 (6H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz), 2.33 (6H, s), 3.95 (3H, s), 3.97 (3H, s), 4.95 (2H, septet, *J* 6.8 Hz), 5.33 (1H, s), 6.26 (1H, s), 6.63 (1H, br s), 6.95 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz), 8.04 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 19.6, 21.7, 21.9, 34.8, 56.2, 61.4, 67.3, 103.3, 107.6, 112.4, 113.5, 122.5, 135.7, 144.9, 147.5, 155.0, 162.8, 165.6 and 166.5; HR-ESI-TOF-MS *m/z* 508.1931 ([M+Na]⁺), calcd. for [C₂₆H₃₁NO₈+Na]⁺ : 508.1942.

Di-tert-butyl 4-(7',8'-dimethoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (22) :

It was obtained as light yellow coloured solid in 60% yield. *R_f* 0.5 (2% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 201–202 °C; IR (cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3310, 3100, 2976, 2933, 1718, 1669, 1602, 1497, 1376, 1320, 1301, 1282, 1148, 1104, 849 and 816; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.34 (18H, s), 2.29 (6H, s), 3.95 (3H, s), 3.96 (3H, s), 5.33 (1H, s), 6.04 (1H, br s), 6.16 (1H, s), 6.88 (1H, d, *J* 9.2 Hz), 8.00 (1H, d, *J* 9.2 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 19.4, 28.2, 35.4, 56.2, 61.4, 80.5, 103.4, 107.5, 111.5,

113.0, 118.4, 122.3, 135.6, 143.9, 155.0, 162.8 and 166.5; HR-ESI-TOF-MS m/z 536.2232 ($[M+Na]^+$), calcd. for $[C_{28}H_{35}NO_8+Na]^+$: 536.2255.

Diethyl 4-(5',7'-dimethoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (23) :

It was obtained as yellow coloured solid in 65% yield. R_f 0.5 (2% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 196–198 °C; IR (cm^{-1} , KBr) : 3358, 3095, 2983, 2940, 1701, 1676, 1599, 1306, 1215, 1121, 1103, 1062 and 857; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.22 (3H, t, J 7.6 Hz), 1.30 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 2.12 (3H, s), 2.46 (3H, s), 3.86 (3H, s), 4.03 (3H, s), 4.10–4.25 (4H, m), 5.88 (1H, d, J 3.2 Hz), 6.18 (1H, s), 6.19 (1H, d, J 4.4 Hz), 6.43 (1H, d, J 4.4 Hz), 6.52 (1H, d, J 2.8 Hz), 6.52 (1H, d, J 3.2 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100.6 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 14.2, 19.6, 21.3, 51.8, 55.8, 56.8, 59.7, 60.2, 94.6, 96.6, 102.5, 104.3, 106.8, 111.8, 149.0, 151.1, 153.4, 156.9, 157.8, 161.3, 162.6, 166.4 and 167.4; HR-ESI-TOF-MS m/z 480.1612 ($[M+Na]^+$), calcd. for $[C_{24}H_{27}NO_8+Na]^+$: 480.1629.

Dimethyl 4-(5',7'-dimethoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (24) :

It was obtained as yellow coloured solid in 68% yield. R_f 0.5 (2% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 217–218 °C; IR (cm^{-1} , KBr) : 3423, 3017, 2950, 2845, 1714, 1602, 1560, 1531, 1493, 1455, 1318, 1212, 1157, 1108, 1057 and 756; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 2.08 (3H, s), 2.41 (3H, s), 3.61 (3H, s), 3.65 (3H, s), 3.81 (3H, s), 3.99 (3H, s), 5.97 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz), 6.09 (1H, s), 6.13 (1H, d, J 4.4 Hz), 6.38 (1H, s), 6.46 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100.6 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 19.4, 21.3, 50.7, 51.3, 51.8, 55.8, 56.8, 94.6, 96.5, 102.4, 104.2, 106.2, 111.8, 149.6, 150.8, 153.7, 156.9, 157.8, 161.2, 162.6, 166.6 and 167.8; HR-ESI-TOF-MS m/z 452.1298 ($[M+Na]^+$), calcd. for $[C_{22}H_{23}NO_8+Na]^+$: 452.1316.

Diallyl 4-(5',7'-dimethoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (25) :

It was obtained as yellow coloured solid in 65% yield. R_f 0.5 (4% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 148–150 °C; IR (cm^{-1} , KBr) : 3345, 3076, 2975, 2937, 1707, 1653, 1648, 1603, 1492, 1457, 1377, 1317, 1203, 1154, 1108 and 915; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 2.10 (3H, s), 2.45 (3H, s), 3.81 (3H, s), 3.98 (3H, s), 4.54–4.60 (4H, m), 5.08–5.31 (4H, m), 5.78–5.96 (2H, m), 5.99 (1H, d, J 4.4 Hz), 6.13 (1H, s), 6.20 (1H, d, J 4.4 Hz), 6.38

(1H, d, J 2.4 Hz), 6.45 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100.6 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 19.7, 21.5, 51.8, 55.8, 56.8, 64.7, 64.8, 94.6, 96.6, 102.4, 104.0, 106.3, 111.8, 117.2, 118.2, 132.4, 132.5, 149.9, 150.8, 154.1, 156.9, 157.8, 161.1, 162.6, 165.8 and 167.0; HR-ESI-TOF-MS m/z 504.1619 ($[M+Na]^+$), calcd. for $[C_{26}H_{23}NO_8+Na]^+$: 504.1629.

Di-iso-propyl 4-(5',7'-dimethoxycoumarin-4'-yl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (26) :

It was obtained as yellow coloured solid in 58% yield. R_f 0.5 (2% methanol in chloroform), m.p. 158–159 °C; IR (cm^{-1} , KBr) : 3328, 3079, 2981, 2933, 1702, 1618, 1603, 1363, 1307, 1251 and 1101; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.17 (3H, d, J 4.4 Hz), 1.23 (3H, d, J 5.2 Hz), 1.26 (3H, d, J 6.0 Hz), 1.30 (3H, d, J 4.8 Hz), 2.11 (3H, s), 2.44 (3H, s), 3.86 (3H, s), 4.02 (3H, s), 4.99–5.07 (2H, m), 5.84 (1H, s), 6.13 (1H, br s), 6.19 (1H, s), 6.42 (1H, s), 6.51 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (100.6 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 19.7, 21.2, 21.8, 21.92, 21.96, 22.1, 51.9, 55.7, 56.8, 67.2, 67.7, 94.6, 96.6, 102.5, 104.6, 107.2, 111.7, 148.5, 151.3, 152.8, 157.0, 157.8, 161.3, 162.5, 166.1 and 167.0; HR-ESI-TOF-MS m/z 508.1934 ($[M+Na]^+$), calcd. for $[C_{26}H_{31}NO_8+Na]^+$: 508.1942.

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